

DEFINITION OF PSYCHIATRY

Psychiatry is the science that is dedicated to the study and treatment of mental illness. According to the psychiatrist, [Dr Marshall Hubsher](#) Its objective is to prevent, diagnose, treat and rehabilitate disorders of the mind.

Psychiatry

Only in the 19th century did mental disorders begin to be treated scientifically as diseases. Until then, people suffering from mental illnesses were locked in asylums and received different treatments with the intention of restoring their reason.

Thanks to literature and cinema, many of the atrocities to which people suffering from mental disorders were subjected decades and centuries ago, who questioned the supposed benefits of treatments, are known. On the other hand, it is worrisome to think that many of today's psychiatric patients are victims of mistreatment, and that so many people roam the streets of the cities talking to themselves, without receiving any kind of assistance from the authorities or, something perhaps more sad, of the other beings of their species, who look the other way.

The German Emil Kraepelin (1856-1926) is often mentioned as the father of psychiatry and responsible for including this science within the field of medicine. From their contributions, psychiatry began to consider both psychological and social factors and biological issues in the treatment of patients.

Dr Marshall Hubsher points out that, therefore psychiatric treatments, can be divided into two main types: biological ones, which can include the supply of medicines and the application of electroshock to act in the brain's biochemistry, and psychotherapeutic ones, which appeal to the techniques of psychology.

Psychiatry has several subspecialties, such as psychopathology (which studies the processes that can lead to mental insanity), psychopharmacology (dedicated to the analysis of the effects of drugs on behavioral, emotional or cognitive treatments) and sexology (the schematic study of human sexuality).

It is known as anti-psychiatry to the set of theories and positions that consider that traditional psychiatry is not beneficial because it uses inadequate medical concepts, is linked to the economic interests of pharmaceutical companies, stigmatizes their patients and even treats people against their own will .

Comparison with psychology

The common people tend to believe that the difference between psychology and psychiatry lies simply in the fact that the former does not include the supply of medications to patients; However, next we will see that the relationship between the two is much more complex.

[The experienced psychiatrist](#), Dr Marshall Hubsher lists their similarities:

- * both are sciences that are dedicated to the mental health care of human beings;

- * both offer the possibility of treating patients through therapy;
- * allow interaction with the other science when this may be beneficial for a patient;
- * both present specialties for children, adolescents and adults.

Next, we will study some of its main differences, both in relation to the application and in formal and academic issues:

- * while to receive the title of psychologist it is necessary to study a degree in Psychology, to become a psychiatrist you must study Medicine and then specialize in this science;
- * As mentioned above, only psychiatrists have the power to prescribe medications;
- * Psychology focuses on the emotional plane, and psychiatry focuses its study in neurology;
- * Regarding its classification, psychology is a social science, while psychiatry is a natural science;
- * Within psychology it is possible to find different branches, such as the clinic. Psychiatry, on the other hand, is itself a branch (of medicine);
- * The time needed to complete both races is different. After completing the medical degree, which is a year longer than psychology, you must complete a specialization in psychiatry and then the corresponding residences.